

A NOVEL METHOD FOR FABRICATING C/C-SiC COMPOSITES VIA 3D PRINTING TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

Ceramic matrix composites, based on reinforcement of carbon fiber and matrix of silicon carbide (C/C-SiC), are prime candidates for high temperature structural materials in aerospace, nuclear and transportation areas due to their refractory nature, high specific strength, high thermal conductivity and excellent tribology performance at elevated temperature. This research has focused on demonstrating the feasibility of using 3D printing technology to make C/C-SiC composites components. Firstly, short carbon fiber composites were prepared through 3D printing process, which serves as the reinforcing framework. The processing parameters were optimized to obtain the 3D objects with high precision. Secondly, C/C preforms with controllable porosity and pore structure were generated by infiltrating with phenolic resin followed by carbonization process. Finally, liquid silicon infiltration (LSI) has been performed using the aforementioned C/C porous preforms to convert part of the carbon to silicon carbide. The microstructure evolution and mechanical properties of the C/C-SiC composites were carefully investigated through various characterization techniques. The major advantages of this method over other ceramic processing techniques are the enhanced capability of making near net shape C/C-SiC composite parts with complex structures, full density as well as high performance at a low cost.